

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TEACHING SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

Eshilov Rusliddin Nomozovich

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

2nd. year Master's student of the Department of Interpretation

E-mail: eshilov91@mail.ru

ANNOTATION

Simultaneous interpretation is one of the newest types of translation, appearing only in the 1920s. Credit for the invention of simultaneous interpretation is given to American businessman Edward Filene. The earliest equipment for simultaneous interpretation (microphones, earphones and switching equipment) was manufactured by IBM. Today the profession of an interpreter has new, more innovative name - conference interpreter, and it is already accepted to call interpreting as conference interpreting. These innovations speak for themselves: it is translation practice of the interpreter who provides conferences, negotiations, presentations or other similar events with simultaneous and consecutive translation. Interpreting is rather difficult multiphase activity which can be engaged after long and labor consuming training in translation skills within translation programs of a bachelor and master degree.

Keywords: *simultaneous interpretation, simultaneous translation research, methodological problems, informal speech.*

Introduction

Simultaneous translation research was studied separately in applied linguistics. The reason of it is methodological problems caused by existence of many languages. Besides, it has been caused by practical use of results of the researches necessary only for a small number of users in comparison with the huge market of applied linguistics.

They needed new methods of teaching foreign languages and acquisitions of skills of informal speech. The first works on the translation were written by professional translators who tried to develop theoretical base for training of specialists in the field of translation studies. Although the first steps in simultaneous translation research were carried out nearly half a century ago, linguists still discuss paradigms concerning simultaneous translation process.

The present thesis's relevance lies in its conformity to linguistic and extralinguistic research of professional simultaneous translation as the type of speech communicative activity that based on translation strategies. In the context of simultaneous translation, the role of these strategies is becoming more and more significant.

Aim of simultaneous translation is to acquaint a reader (or listener) who doesn't know foreign languages with the text (or content of oral speech) as much as possible .

As a rule, implementation of simultaneous translation requires the necessary accompanying equipment by means of which speech of the speaker moves via earphones, and the translator speaks in the microphone from where the translation is broadcast for listeners. Thanks to such a device the voice of the translator doesn't hinder to listen to the speaker

Simultaneous interpretation is a relatively recent invention, requiring the use of sophisticated equipment and a high level of advanced education in specific techniques and methods. Because the ability to interpret simultaneously is considered to be both demanding and difficult, it is surprising if not implausible to imagine someone with natural skill interpreting in this way without formal instruction.

Four major linguistic features of simultaneous translation process:

1. Increase of the text during the translation from one language to the other language. It is explained by absence of opportunity to fulfill formulations of the source text carefully.

2. Speed of reproduction of verbal and cogitative process of the translator. Here Shiryaev says that each translator has own individual speed and rate of simultaneous

translation (some translators turn out to be quicker the others on the contrary, to be more moderate).

3. Presence of pauses in the speech of simultaneous translators. We suggest that simultaneous translator needs to do pauses in his speech to be guided in the initial speech.

4. Incomplete expansion of statements. Simultaneous translators keep convolution of the internal speech in the external speech in target language with fast speech tempo of the speaker and lack of time.

Conclusion

Thus, Simultaneous interpretation helps to break down language barriers around the world. No matter which language a delegate communicates in, he or she can easily follow the speaker in real-time now with the help of simultaneous interpretation.

REFERENCES

1. Fotini Apostolou.
2. International Journal of Applied Linguistics. 16.3 (2006)
3. Interpreting for Europe. <http://www-facebook>.
4. Koskinen, Kaisa. Translating Institutions An Ethnographic Study of European Translation and Interpreting .
5. Fairclough, I., & Fairclough, N. (2012).